

Automated Foot Length Measurement Using OpenCV

Akhil Shine
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
akhilshine02@gmail.com

Mr. Ajith G S
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala
gsajith@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— In order to improve the footwear selection process, this research provides a novel way for automating the measurement of foot length using image processing techniques. Our method starts with preprocessing the input image, transforming it to the HSV color space, and using Gaussian blurring to decrease noise. It makes use of Python and a number of libraries, including OpenCV, Scikit-learn, NumPy, Matplotlib, and Imutils. The pre-processed image is then segmented using the K-means clustering algorithm, which makes it easier to identify different foot regions. Clear foot outlines are subsequently extracted from the clustered image using canny edge detection. After that, the foot region within the edge-detected image is localized using contour identification and bounding box extraction. Lastly, the foot size is calculated in centimeters using the bounding box measurements and the original foot image. Images representing saved intermediate findings are used to provide visual feedback during the procedure. This project provides an automated technique for measuring foot length, which may find use in the design of footwear. Our methodology improves user experience and pleasure by expediting the process of measuring feet, which in turn improves the accuracy and efficiency of footwear choices.

Keywords— Footwear, Foot Length Measurement, Image Processing, Automation, Python.

I. INTRODUCTION

Choosing the right shoes is essential to guaranteeing comfort and avoiding foot-related problems. Unfortunately, the conventional techniques for measuring feet are frequently laborious and subjective, producing unreliable findings. In order to overcome this problem, our study proposes a novel approach for automating the assessment of foot length using image processing techniques. Through the use of Python and a number of libraries, such as OpenCV, Scikit-learn, NumPy, Matplotlib, and Imutils, our method seeks to improve the process of choosing shoes by making the process of measuring feet more efficient.

The technique starts with preprocessing the input image, then applies Gaussian blurring to remove noise and converts it to the HSV color space. The K-means clustering algorithm then segments the pre-processed image, facilitating the identification of distinct foot regions. We then extract clear foot outlines from the clustered image using canny edge detection. Next, we use contour identification and bounding box extraction to localize the foot region within the edge-detected image. Finally, we calculate the foot size in centimeters using the bounding box measurements and the original foot image.

The visual feedback during the procedure, in the form of saved intermediate results as photographs, provides an effective method for automating the measurement of foot length. This system could greatly increase the accuracy and effectiveness

of choosing footwear, thereby improving consumer satisfaction.

II. RELATED WORKS

- A. The paper "Research and Development of Information Technology for Determining Shoe Size by Image" et al. [1] addresses the issue of determining shoe size from a two-dimensional photograph of an adult's foot contour. The researchers utilized an actual dataset consisting of images of an A4 sheet, capturing the contours of feet from various angles and lighting conditions. Three key steps comprised their methodology: putting in place a scanner to convert photos to paper sheets, segmenting data based on color using k-means clustering, and measuring foot length in accordance with EU standards.
- B. The applicability of Canny Edge detection methods for measuring foot sizes was examined by the authors of "Computer Vision-Based Foot Measurement Using Modified Canny Edge Algorithms" et al. [2]. They devised an apparatus for capturing images and applied image processing methods to accurately measure foot size. The study used statistical tests to assess the accuracy of the suggested system, taking into account variables including the foot's contrast with the background, its divergence from the platform center, and the Canny Edge algorithm's threshold settings.
- C. The work "Virtual Shoe Fitting System that Uses Augmented Reality to Measure Feet and Try on Shoes" et al. [3] is another pertinent contribution. This technology uses augmented reality to determine shoe size and virtually test shoes, helping to overcome the drawbacks of online shoe shopping. Before making a purchase, users can evaluate shoe comfort by seeing pressure areas on their feet, which improves the online shopping experience.
- D. Lastly, the difficulty Malaysian women have in finding well-fitting shoes is addressed in the paper "Malaysian Women Shoe Sizing System Using Multivariate Normal Probability Distribution" et al. [4]. Through the application of statistical techniques, including multivariate normal distribution, the researchers established shoe size categories according to foot measurements. Their research offers important information for creating a prototype shoe size system that is suited to Malaysian women, which will ultimately enhance the comfort and fit of footwear.
- E. "Virtual Fit using Computer Vision and Trimesh" et al. [5] offers a fresh take on virtual changing rooms,

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11183705](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183705)

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

tackling the prevalent problem of customers being unhappy with online purchases because of fit inconsistencies. Using any online image, the suggested system enables users to virtually try on shoes, shirts, and pants, among other things. Unlike current solutions, it provides a more adaptable and user-focused virtual fitting experience by not requiring the upkeep of vast product databases or limiting users to particular websites.

- F. "Shoes recommendation system based on clustering of 3D shoe data" et al. [6] developed a recommendation system based on three-dimensional foot and shoe data clustering to address the problem of size mismatches in online shoe purchases. By giving consumers precise shoe size suggestions based on their foot proportions, this approach attempted to lessen the issue of size mismatch.
- G. "Study on the changes of foot size in pregnant women" et al. [7] looked into how pregnant women's feet changed in size, taking into account variables such as foot length, heel girth, ankle girth, and arch height. The results of the study demonstrated considerable increases in foot dimensions during pregnancy, offering important information for selecting and designing shoes that are appropriate for the needs of expectant mothers.
- H. "Object Size Measurement through Images: An Application to Measuring Human Foot Size" et al. [8] proposed an end-to-end system for determining a person's foot size from photographs. In order to precisely extract foot boundaries and adjust scale variance in foot size for measurements, this method used color mask segmentation in conjunction with a linear regression model.

III. METHODOLOGY

This system uses image processing techniques to automate the process of determining shoe sizes. Preprocessing the input image, extracting pertinent features, and precisely calculating the foot size all require multiple stages, as well as the use of Python and a number of libraries, including Matplotlib, OpenCV, Scikit-learn, NumPy, and Imutils. The methodology's components include:

A. Image Preprocessing:

Using OpenCV, transform the input image to the HSV color space to start the preprocessing step. This conversion is required for other image processing processes. We subject the HSV image to Gaussian blurring to minimize noise and ensure more seamless processing.

```
def preprocess(img):
    img = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_RGB2HSV)
    img = cv2.GaussianBlur(img, ksize=(9, 9), sigmaX=0)
    img = img/255
    return img
```

B. K-Means Clustering:

Next, using an unsupervised learning technique from the Scikit-learn library, the preprocessed image is put through K-Means Clustering. By iteratively updating cluster centroids to minimize the within-cluster sum of squared distances, K-means clustering seeks to group comparable pixels together. K-Means clustering makes it easier to identify

different foot regions within the image by dividing the image into discrete regions based on pixel similarity.

```
def kMeans_cluster(img):
    image_2D = img.reshape(img.shape[0]*img.shape[1], img.shape[2])
    kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=2, random_state=0).fit(image_2D)
    clustOut = kmeans.cluster_centers_[kmeans.labels_]
    clustered_3D = clustOut.reshape(img.shape[0], img.shape[1], img.shape[2])
    clusteredImg = np.uint8(clustered_3D*255)
    return clusteredImg
```

C. Edge Detection:

Following picture clustering, this technique extracts distinct foot outlines from the clustered image.

```
def edgeDetection(clusteredImage):
    edged1 = cv2.Canny(clusteredImage, 0, 255)
    edged = cv2.dilate(edged1, kernel=None, iterations=1)
    edged = cv2.erode(edged, kernel=None, iterations=1)
    return edged
```

D. Contour Detection and Bounding Box Extraction:

The foot region is then located inside the edge-detected image using contour identification and bounding box extraction techniques. These stages enable the precise definition of the foot area, which is crucial for accurate measurement of foot length.

```
def getBoundingBox(img):
    contours, _ = cv2.findContours(img, cv2.RETR_TREE, cv2.CHAIN_APPROX_SIMPLE)
    contours = sorted(contours, key=lambda x: cv2.contourArea(x), reverse=True)
    contours_poly = [None]*len(contours)
    boundRect = [None]*len(contours)
    for i, c in enumerate(contours):
        contours_poly[i] = cv2.approxPolyDP(c, epsilon=3, closed=True)
        boundRect[i] = cv2.boundingRect(contours_poly[i])
    return boundRect, contours, contours_poly, img
```

E. Foot Size Calculation:

To ensure exact isolation of the crucial area, we finally crop the original image using the bounding rectangle of the foot region. Then, we isolate the foot region for further analysis by superimposing the cropped foot image onto a blank canvas. Lastly, we use the cropped foot image's dimensions to compute the foot size, giving precise measurements that are crucial for choosing the right shoes.

```
def cropOrig(bRect, oimg):
    x, y, w, h = bRect
    pcroppedImg = oimg[y:y+h, x:x+w]
    x1, y1, w1, h1 = 0, 0, pcroppedImg.shape[1], pcroppedImg.shape[0]
    y2 = int(h1 / 10)
    x2 = int(w1 / 10)
    crop1 = pcroppedImg[y1 + y2:h1 - y2, x1 + x2:w1 - x2]
    ix, iy, iw, ih = x + x2, y + y2, crop1.shape[1], crop1.shape[0]
    croppedImg = oimg[iy:iy+ih, ix:ix+iw]
    return croppedImg, pcroppedImg

def overlayImage(croppedImg, pcroppedImg):
    x1, y1, w1, h1 = 0, 0, pcroppedImg.shape[1], pcroppedImg.shape[0]
    y2 = int(h1 / 10)
    x2 = int(w1 / 10)
    new_image = np.zeros(shape=(pcroppedImg.shape[0], pcroppedImg.shape[1], 3), np.uint8)
    new_image[:, 0:pcroppedImg.shape[1]] = (255, 0, 0) # (B, G, R)
    new_image[y1 + y2:y1 + y2 + croppedImg.shape[0], x1 + x2:x1 + x2 + croppedImg.shape[1]] = croppedImg
    return new_image
```

```
def calcFeetSize(pcroppedImg, fboundRect):
    x1, y1, w1, h1 = 0, 0, pcroppedImg.shape[1], pcroppedImg.shape[0]
    y2 = int(h1 / 10)
    x2 = int(w1 / 10)
    fh = y2 + fboundRect[2][3]
    fw = x2 + fboundRect[2][2]
    ph = pcroppedImg.shape[0]
    pw = pcroppedImg.shape[1]
    opw = 210
    oph = 297
    ofs = 0.0
    if fw > fh:
        ofs = (opw / pw) * fw
    else:
        ofs = (oph / ph) * fh
    return ofs
```

By ensuring precise and effective measurement of foot sizes from input photographs, this technology makes it easier for consumers to choose the right shoe size.

IV. RESULT

Upload Image!

- Choose an image file to upload using the form above. Accepted formats: JPEG, PNG, JPG.
- Click the image from a minimum distance of 15 cm.
- Click the image as shown above.

Figure 1. Input User Interface

Figure 2. Input Image

Foot Size Measurement Result

Predicted foot size (cm): **26.81830985915493**

You can go for size: **8**

Figure3.Input Image

Figure 4. Accuracy of Input Image

Figure 5. Plot Scatter

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the built system effectively uses machine learning algorithms and image processing techniques to automate the process of determining shoe sizes. Through the application of techniques including contour analysis, edge detection, and K-means clustering, the system is able to precisely locate and quantify the foot region in input photos.

The implemented code calculates the foot size precisely, retrieves pertinent information from the photos, and preprocesses them effectively. Combining these methods into a unified system makes shoe selection easier and more user-friendly, thereby improving overall satisfaction.

We can investigate additional improvements and optimizations in the future to increase the system's accuracy and resilience. Iterative testing and user feedback can also improve the system's functionality and identify any possible drawbacks. All things considered, the developed system has a great deal of potential to transform the footwear sector by providing a smooth and automated method of determining shoe size.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Sakharov, K. Smelyakov and O. Bohomolov, "Research and Development of Information Technology for Determining Shoe Size by Image," 2023 IEEE Open Conference of Electrical, Electronic and Information Sciences (eStream), Vilnius, Lithuania, 2023, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/eStream59056.2023.10135036.
- [2] H. Bizen, M. Yoshida, M. Jimbu and Y. Kawai, "Virtual Shoe Fitting System that Uses Augmented Reality to Measure Feet and Try on Shoes," 2021 IEEE 3rd Global Conference on Life Sciences and Technologies (LifeTech), Nara, Japan, 2021, pp. 217-219, doi: 10.1109/LifeTech52111.2021.9391966.
- [3] V. Kishore Kumar Rejeti, S. Abdul, P. H. Prasanth, S. Ashok and S. M. Sameer, "Virtual Fit using Computer Vision and Trimesh," 2023 Second International Conference on Electronics and Renewable Systems (ICEARS), Tuticorin, India, 2023, pp. 1590-1595, doi: 10.1109/ICEARS56392.2023.10084945.

- [4] M. F. Mohd Hamzah, O. Mohd Rijal, K. Kimura and N. Mohd Noor, "Malaysian Women Shoe Sizing System Using Multivariate Normal Probability Distribution," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 142726-142737, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2944763.
- [5] R. R. Allorde, C. Fornoles and M. V. Caya, "Computer Vision-Based Foot Measurement Using Modified Canny Edge Algorithm," 2023 IEEE 5th Eurasia Conference on IOT, Communication and Engineering (ECICE), Yunlin, Taiwan, 2023, pp. 416-420, doi: 10.1109/ECICE59523.2023.10383174.
- [6] J. Matsuki, Y. Manabe, N. Yata, K. Nomura and Hirohito, "Shoes recommendation system based on clustering of 3D shoes data," 2018 International Workshop on Advanced Image Technology (IWAIT), Chiang Mai, Thailand, 2018, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/IWAIT.2018.8369676.
- [7] N. -C. Weng, C. -F. Wu, S. -B. Wang, K. -C. Lin and Y. -C. Huang, "Study on the changes of foot size in pregnant women," 2018 1st IEEE International Conference on Knowledge Innovation and Invention (ICKII), Jeju, Korea (South), 2018, pp. 199-202, doi: 10.1109/ICKII.2018.8569173.
- [8] M. A. Shahid, M. A. Iftikhar, Z. A. Gondal, M. Adnan and S. Rathore, "Object Size Measurement through Images: An Application to Measuring Human Foot Size," 2018 International Conference on Frontiers of Information Technology (FIT), Islamabad, Pakistan, 2018, pp. 298-302, doi: 10.1109/FIT.2018.00059.